

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 7: Course Evaluation Pre-Training Questionnaire

Page 1: Information and Consent Reaffirmation

We would like to learn more about **outreach activities among research support infrastructures and open science initiatives**. This questionnaire will ask you about the outreach activities you engage in for your initiative and the barriers you face to doing this.

We are defining outreach activities as **anything which reaches out to and/or engages the community around your initiative**. This includes (but is not limited to) making social media posts, sending newsletters, community building activities, hosting events, creating podcasts, writing which is aimed at sharing your initiative such as blogs or journal articles, vlogging, and collecting feedback from the community.

This project is designed in line with the British Psychological Society (2021) Code of Human Research Ethics. We expect that the decision to participate or not participate is within the professional remit of participants. All responses are anonymous. [<add information about ethics approval>](#) For more information, see the full participant information sheet [<add link>](#). We recommend that you download this for future reference.

We anticipate that this survey will take most people 15 minutes to complete.

Please note that aggregate responses may be shared with other workshop attendees via charts and word clouds.

If you have questions or concerns, please contact the researcher:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator
bethan@we-are-ols.org

Please indicate your consent to taking part by checking the boxes below:

- I have read and agreed to the terms and conditions outlined in the participant information sheet.
- I consent to taking part in this study.

We will be linking responses to the questionnaires using unique identifiers. Please create your unique identifier using the following:

- Your favourite dessert. If you don't know what your favourite dessert is, please enter your favourite colour, book, movie, etc.
- Your month of birth as a number.
- The first two letters of your mother's first name.

Please put a hyphen (-) between each element of the identifier.

For example: someone whose favourite dessert is tiramisu, who was born in January, and whose mother is called Mary would enter tiramisu-01-ma.

Please enter your code below:

Page 2: Outreach activities

As a reminder, we are defining outreach activities as anything which **reaches out to and/or engages the community around your open science initiative**. This could include a range of marketing and communications activities, such as managing social media accounts, newsletters, or events.

What outreach activities are you currently engaged in for the open science initiative(s) you are part of?

- Creating social media posts
- Managing email lists or sending newsletters
- Blogging
- Academic writing, such as preprints or journal articles
- Hosting events (e.g. hackathons, conference sessions)
- Collecting feedback, such as user research
- Creating podcasts
- Creating video content, such as vlogs or TikToks
- Community building activities
- Other (please specify): _____

Which outreach activities for the open science initiative(s) you are part of would you like to try in the future?

- Creating social media posts
- Managing email lists or sending newsletters
- Blogging

- Academic writing, such as preprints or journal articles
- Hosting events (e.g. hackathons, conference sessions)
- Collecting feedback, such as user research
- Creating podcasts
- Creating video content, such as vlogs or TikToks
- Community building activities
- Other (please specify): _____
- None of the above

Page 3: Barriers

What stops you from engaging in outreach activities for your open science initiative(s)?

Knowledge and skills

- I don't know how to create useful or effective outreach resources
- I lack the necessary skills, such as graphic design
- I'm not confident that I can represent the initiative correctly
- I'm not sure which channels to use (for example, which social media platforms to post on)

Prioritisation and resources

- I don't have enough time to do outreach activities
- I don't enjoy doing outreach activities
- My community don't have enough time to engage in my outreach
- I do not have enough resources for outreach activities
- Outreach activities are not prioritised within my initiative
- My initiative doesn't feel like a finished product that can be shared

Community and environment

- It feels like we're competing with other initiatives
- I'm not sure who to ask for help
- Lack of interest from the community
- There is too much content and I can't break through the noise

Something else (please specify): _____

Page 4: Knowledge

The OSPARK-aligned answer is highlighted in light green.

Below is a series of 9 questions about outreach strategy. These questions will assess whether your approach aligns with OSPARK's course content. Remember that there is no "right" answer with social media strategy—every person and initiative needs a tailored approach.

Who might be in the target market for an open science initiative?

- Students
- Researchers in academia
- Researchers in industry, the public sector, or nonprofit organisations
- Research professionals and support staff, such as lab managers and librarians
- Research funders and philanthropists
- University administrators
- All of the above
- I'm not sure

Conference talks and networking sessions are a form of marketing for your open science initiative.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

Which communications channel should you use to advertise your open science initiative?

- The ones with the most overall users
- The ones frequently used by the people I want to reach
- The ones which are easily accessible through my job
- I'm not sure

What is the most effective strategy to grow your open science initiative's social media page?

- Occasionally commenting on and sharing other initiatives' work
- Spending 1 hour per day "liking" every post on the account's timeline
- Using 20+ hashtags in every post, on every platform
- I'm not sure

What is most important in a talk about your open science initiative?

- Providing clear information about the initiative
- Connecting emotionally with the audience
- Both are equally important
- I'm not sure

What is the main benefit of short vertical videos, such as TikToks or YouTube Shorts, over long-form videos?

- There is often better discoverability through wider algorithmic reach
- Viewers are more likely to look at your profile and other content
- It's easier to establish a connection with the audience
- I'm not sure

Marketing and communications are primarily about...

- Promoting your open science initiative
- Providing value to your audience
- I'm not sure

Interacting with similar or competing open science initiatives is harmful to your open science initiative's marketing and communications goals.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

What would normally be included in a marketing and communications strategy plan?

- Broad guidance about the goals, style, tone, and channels you will use
- Specific step-by-step instructions on how to create each social media post
- I'm not sure

This is an attention check. Please select "false" to show that you are paying attention.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

Page 5: Self-efficacy

Imagine you were asked to conduct outreach activities for the open science initiative(s) you

are part of. How confident would you feel doing this?

1. Not at all confident
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
5. Very confident

Please think about conducting outreach activities for an open science initiative. When you think about these activities, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Note: Rated on a 5-point Likert scale: strongly disagree (1), slightly disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), slightly agree (4), strongly agree (5).

- I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself.
- When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.
- In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.
- I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.
- I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges.
- I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.
- Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.
- Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.
- This is an attention check. Please choose "slightly agree" to show that you are paying attention.

Page 6: Training needs

What resources have you seen (online or offline) about promotion, outreach, marketing, and communications for open science?

If you were to join a training programme about outreach activities for open science initiatives, what skills or knowledge would you most like to develop?

If you were to join a training programme about outreach activities for open science initiatives, how would you prefer the training to be delivered? Choose all that apply.

Online

- In-person
- Hybrid (online and in-person components)

Why did you choose this format (or these formats)?

Page 7: Demographics

How long have you been involved in open science?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-5 years
- More than 5 years

How would you describe your career stage?

- Exploration (student)
- Establishment (junior role, e.g. postdoctoral researcher)
- Mid-career (a role which involves managing or mentoring more junior colleagues, e.g. senior lecturer/associate professor)
- Late-career (a senior role, e.g. professor)
- Retired

Which region are you resident in?

- Africa
- Antarctica
- Asia
- Europe
- Latin America or the Caribbean
- Oceania
- USA or Canada

Which region(s) did you reside in before the age of 18?

- Africa
- Antarctica
- Asia
- Europe
- Latin America or the Caribbean
- Oceania
- USA or Canada

What species are you? This is an attention check. To show that you are paying attention, please type "cat" in the box below.

Which of the following platforms do you use to find out more about open science?

- Academic writing (preprints, journal articles)
- Blogs
- Bluesky
- Events (such as conferences, hackathons)
- LinkedIn
- Mailing lists
- Mastodon
- Podcasts
- Repositories (such as Zenodo)
- X (formerly Twitter)
- Video platforms (such as YouTube or TikTok)
- Websites (such as those belonging to initiatives or universities)
- Word of mouth
- Other (please specify): -----

Page 8: Closing message

Thank you for completing this questionnaire. You will receive a follow-up questionnaire when the OSPARK Bootcamp finishes.

If you have questions or concerns, please contact the researcher:

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